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Customer Demographics and Impulsive Behavior in Apparel Outlets

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Abstract

This paper attempts to explore the effect of demographic factors on young customers' apparel impulse buying behavior. The purpose of this study is to investigate the difference in the impulse buying tendency of young customers due to various demographic factors (age, gender, marital status, income, educational qualification and occupation). To attain this objective a study was carried out among shoppers in the age group of 16-35 years. Research approach used is quantitative in nature. Hypotheses were developed to analyze the differences in customers' impulse buying tendency on the basis of various demographic characteristics. Questionnaires were administered to 677 shoppers who constituted the sample. These were shoppers who were visiting retail outlets at various shopping malls in different parts of Bangalore, India. Statistical tools like one way ANOVA, independent sample t-test and descriptive techniques were used to derive results from the data collected with the help of SPSS 20.0. The results revealed that gender was the only variable which had a significant effect on the customers' impulse buying tendency.

Keywords: 1.Age, 2.Education, 3.Gender, 4.Impulse Buying Tendency, 5.Income, 6.Occupation.

Introduction

India is one of the most desirable retail destinations in the world. Its twin growth engines of economic growth and demographic profile, set it apart from other nations and present a compelling business case for global retailers looking to enter the market. Retailing industry is the second largest employer after agriculture, has witnessed significant transformation since 1995. Traditionally, the Indian retail sector was characterised by the presence of a large number of small family-owned mom-and-pop stores. With the liberalisation of the economy in the 1990s, modern retail formats began to develop, and Indian business houses and manufacturers started investing in this sector, which enjoyed double-digit growth in the past 15 years. The growing Indian market has attracted many foreign retailers and Indian corporate to invest in this sector. With growth in modern formats, traditional retailers are quickly changing their business models, implementing new technologies and modern accounting practices to face the competition. According to IBEF (2015) report, India's retail sector has seen many changes in the last decade and is regarded as one of the pillars of the economy. It accounts for 14-15 per cent of the GDP and employs about 40 million people. The retail industry has been significantly contributing to the GDP, employment and the economy. India remains an appealing, long-term retail destination for several reasons, starting with its demography – half of India's population is less than 30 years of age and roughly one-third of the population lives in cities. The disposable income of Indians is increasing – allowing them to spend more and try new products, brands, and categories.

High consumer spending over the years by the young population and sharp rise in disposable income are driving the Indian organised retail sector's growth.

A great deal of research focuses on how consumers shop, but the rationale behind their chosen behaviors remains somewhat underserved. Research revealed that people experience different buying behaviour in different situations, some are spontaneous while other are well thought of. Impulse buying has always been considered as an important behaviour in consumer decision making. Impulse buying occurs when a customer sees the product in a shop and the inner feelings strongly urge the customer to purchase and bring it into possession. Retailers have long realized the power of impulse buying, which is indeed a central point in many purchasing activities. They are well aware that a sizable portion of their sales volume is generated by impulsive purchase, with over 50 per cent of mall shoppers buying items on impulse (Dawson and Kim, 2010). Impulse buying is a widely prevalent phenomenon around the world. The powerful influence of impulse behaviour on consumer buying suggests it is an important area of study (Bayley and Nancarrow, 1998; Hausman, 2000). Researchers found that impulse buyers usually do not set out with the specific purpose of visiting a certain store and purchasing a certain item; the behaviour occurs after experiencing an urge to buy (Beatty and Ferrell, 1998), and such behaviours are influenced by internal states and environmental/external factors. Since impulse buying is a pervasive aspect of consumers' behaviours and a focal point for strategic marketing plans (Rook, 1987), it is worthwhile for retailers to understand factors that trigger consumers' impulsive reactions. For the past few years the marketers have realized that impulse buying can generate huge profits if appropriate marketing techniques are used. The literature says that a number of factors affect impulse buying behaviour out of which, the impact of demographic variables on the impulse buying behaviour has always been a matter of discussion among the researchers (Bhuvanewari and Krishnan, 2015; Awan and Abbas, 2015). Therefore, it is important for the marketers to study the impact of demographic factors like age, gender, marital status, income, occupation and education on impulse buying as an emerging pattern. This paper attempts to identify and explain the impact of demographic factors on impulse buying among young customers in apparel outlets.

Literature Review

Impulse Buying Behavior:

Impulse buying is a major research issue among consumer behavior researchers not only because of its complexities, but also its widespread prevalence across a broad range of product categories (Applebaum, 1951; Baumeister, 2002; Beatty and Ferrell, 1998; Clover, 1950; Kacen and Lee, 2002; Ramanathan and Menon, 2006; Rook, 1987; Vohs and Faber, 2007). In a research conducted by Cobb and Hoyer (1986), impulse buying was defined as an unplanned purchase and this definition can also be found in the research of Kollat and Willett (1967). Research by Rook (1987) reported that impulse buying usually takes place, when a consumer feels a forceful motivation that turns into a desire to purchase a commodity instantly. Mathai and Haridas (2014) defined impulse buying as unplanned purchase behavior due to a sudden desire to buy the product for self-gratification. Beatty and Ferrell (1998) defined impulse buying as instantaneous purchase having no previous aim or objective to purchase the commodity. Stern (1962) found that products bought on impulse are usually cheap. Impulse buying is defined as an unplanned, which is characterized by both relatively rapid decision making, and a subjective bias for immediate possession (Rook and Gardner, 1993). Impulse buying is associated with consumer

impulsiveness (CI) trait, positively (Puri, 1996). The powerful influence of impulse behavior on consumer buying suggests it is an important area of study (Bayley and Nancarrow, 1998). Stern (1962) provided the foundation for defining impulse buying behavior by classifying the act as planned, unplanned, or impulse. Rook and Fisher (1995) define the buying impulsiveness trait as “a consumer’s tendency to buy spontaneously, unreflectively, immediately and kinetically”. The marketing literature describes impulse buying as an unplanned purchase made as a consequence of sudden, powerful and persistent urge to buy products immediately (Beatty and Ferrell, 1998; Rook, 1987). Kacen and Lee (2002) reported that impulse buying has been lately conceptualized as a sudden, compelling, hedonically complex purchasing behavior in which the rapidity of the purchase decision process excludes thoughtful, deliberate consideration of all information and choice. Impulse buying is also described as a form of hedonic rather than utilitarian shopping behavior underpinned by several pervasive emotional motivations (Sharma, et al., 2010). The unplanned nature of the purchase is central to the definition of impulse buying (Piron, 1991).

Factors influencing Impulse Buying:

There are a lot of studies on various factors affecting impulse buying. Stern (1962) characterized nine factors affecting impulse buying (low price, marginal need for an item, mass distribution, self-service, mass advertising, prominent store display, short product life, small size or light weight, and ease of storage). In addition, there are other studies that investigate the role of various factors on impulse buying. For example the researches of Beatty and Ferrell (1998); Hausman (2000); Rook and Gardner (1993); Youn and Faber (2000) found that emotions and feelings strongly influence buying behaviors, which result in consumer impulse buying. Babin and Babin (2001) found that in stores consumers’ purchasing intentions and spending can largely be influenced by emotions. Impulse buying behavior is motivated by a powerful urge (Verplanken and Herabadi, 2001) and feelings of pleasure and excitement (Hausman, 2000; Rook, 1987; Rook and Fisher, 1995; Ramanathan and Menon, 2002; Peck and Childers, 2006). Some other internal, personal-related factors thought to influence the act of impulse buying are: educational experience (Wood, 1998) and mood states (Rook and Gardner, 1993). Stores are the place where buyers buy products, whether it’s planned or unplanned purchase. It only depends on the personal income, which indicates how much and how many times he or she visits shopping stores to buy products (Tirmizi et al, 2009). Previous researches have shown that different factors impact impulsive purchasing behavior, including the presence of others (Luo, 2005), the consumer's mood (Beatty and Ferrell, 1998; Rook and Gardner, 1993), trait impulsiveness (Jones et al., 2003; Rook and Fisher, 1995; Weun et al., 1998), product category impulsiveness (Jones et al., 2003), evaluation of the appropriateness of engaging in impulse buying (Rook and Fisher, 1995), individual and environmental touch (Peck and Childers, 2006), self-identity (Dittmar et al., 1995; Lee and Kacen, 1999), cultural orientation (Kacen and Lee, 2002; Lee and Kacen, 1999), as well as demographic characteristics such as gender (e.g., Dittmar et al., 1995; Rook and Gardner, 1993) and age (e.g., Helmers et al., 1995; Wood, 1998). A few studies have found the significant interactions between impulse buying and demographics such as age, gender and income. However, no research was found that investigated impact of various demographic characteristics of customers like age, gender, marital status, income, educational qualification and occupation on impulse buying behaviour. To draw reliable conclusions, empirical research is needed. So we will investigate

the effects of demographic factors on young customers' impulse buying behaviour towards apparel.

Research Hypotheses:

In this study demographic analysis is done to test if there is any difference in the impulse buying tendency of the customers due to age, gender, marital status, income, education and occupation. The following hypotheses have been developed which will enable us to analyse the difference in the customers' impulse buying tendency on the basis of demographic characteristics.

- H₁: Impulse buying tendency varies significantly among the customers of different age groups.*
- H₂: Impulse buying tendency differs significantly between male and female customers.*
- H₃: Impulse buying tendency varies significantly among customers with different occupational status.*
- H₄: Impulse buying tendency differs significantly between single and married customer.*
- H₅: Impulse buying tendency varies significantly among customers with different educational qualification.*
- H₆: Impulse buying tendency varies significantly among customers of various income groups.*

Research Methodology

Research approach and sample design:

The study was intended to focus on the impact of demographic factors on young customers' impulse buying tendency in terms of apparel segment as a product category. The research design used is descriptive in nature. The sample size of the research was 700 but 23 were outliers hence, the revised sample size was 677. The convenient sampling technique was adopted. Customers who walk out of the store were surveyed with the help of a structured questionnaire. Thus, sampling procedure is purposive sampling. The survey was conducted in Top six Malls-ranked on the basis of number of visitors- of Bangalore city for a month.

Instrument design:

The research objective was to understand the impact of demographic factors on young customers' impulse buying behaviour. The questionnaire used for the research comprised of questions on demographic variables— age, gender, occupation, marital status, educational qualification, and income. The impulse buying tendency was measured using a five point LIKERT scale, with one denoting never and five denoting always. Respondents were asked to circle the number that best described their response.

Data analysis methods:

Data collected were entered into an Excel file. The data file was imported from Excel to the Statistical Packages for Social Sciences' (SPSS) software for analysis. Statistical methods used in the data analysis in this study were descriptive statistics and frequency tests, one way ANOVA, and independent sample t-test. The significance level chosen for this study was 0.05. First, descriptive statistics and frequency tables were generated both for demographic factors and impulse buying tendency. One way ANOVA was used to test the differences in the impulse buying tendency of young customers across various age groups, occupational

status, educational qualification, and income groups. Independent sample t-test was conducted to check the difference in customers' impulse buying tendency on the basis of gender and marital status.

Analysis and Discussion:

Demographic analysis is the statistical analysis of the size, composition and spatial distribution of human population. Demographic analysis helps in understanding the human profile of respondents of a survey and relating it to their responses to arrive at conclusive patterns and trends. These patterns and trends have practical applications in planning, designing and executing specific activities.

Descriptive statistics for demographics:

Descriptive statistics for the sample can be found in table-1, providing information regarding the respondents' demographic profile, such as age, gender, occupation, marital status, educational qualification and individual income per month. The majority of the respondents were in the age group 21-25 years (54.1%), 16-20 years (24.4%), 26-30 years (18.6%), whereas only 3% of 31-35 years of age. Almost one half (52.7%) of the respondents were male and the other half (47.3%) were female customers. The gender uniformity has been taken into account in order not to affect the result in a negative way, favouring one gender over the other. The majority of respondents were students, as expected (45.1%), 42.1% were employed, 6.6% were unemployed, 4.3% were professionals, and 1.9% were businessmen/others. Most respondents (87.3%) were single and 12.7% were married. The largest proportion (34.1%) of the respondents were graduates, followed by intermediates (33.4), post-graduates (30%), and 2.5% were others. Almost one-half (47.8%) of the respondents were dependent on either parents' or others' income, 26.2% of the respondents' income range was Rs.10, 000- 25,000, 12.7% of the respondents' income range was Rs.26,000- 50,000, 7.8% of the respondents belong to below Rs. 10,000 income group, and only 5.5% of the respondents' income range is Rs.51, 000 and above.

Table-1: Descriptive statistics for demographics of customers

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Age	16 – 20 years	165	24.4
	21 – 25 years	366	54.1
	26 – 30 years	126	18.6
	31 – 35 years	20	3.0
	Total	677	100.0
Gender	Male	357	52.7
	Female	320	47.3
	Total	677	100.0
Occupation	Employed	285	42.1
	Unemployed	45	6.6
	Professional	29	4.3
	Business/others	13	1.9
	Student	305	45.1
	Total	677	100.0
Marital Status	Single	591	87.3
	Married	86	12.7

	Total	677	100.0
Educational Qualification	Intermediate	226	33.4
	Graduation	231	34.1
	Post-Graduation	203	30.0
	Other	17	2.5
	Total	677	100
Income	Below Rs. 10,000	52	7.7
	Rs.10, 000- 25,000	178	26.3
	Rs.26,000- 50,000	86	12.7
	Rs.51, 000 and above	37	5.5
	Dependent on parents' / others' income	324	47.9
	Total	677	100

Source: Primary source

Table-2: Descriptive Statistics for impulse buying tendency

Particulars	Number of cases	Mean	S.D.
Impulse Buying Tendency	677	3.03	0.631
1. I go shopping to change my mood.	677	2.67	1.180
2. I buy things spontaneously.	677	2.91	1.121
3. I feel a sense of excitement when I make an impulse purchase.	677	3.12	1.169
4. I have difficulty controlling my urge of buying when I see a good offer.	677	3.15	1.215
5. When I see a good deal, I tend to buy more than what I intended to buy.	677	3.33	1.203

Source: Primary source

Descriptive Statistics for impulse buying tendency:

As a five-point Likert scale, which ranged from never=1 to frequently=5, was used to measure impulse buying tendency, a score of above 3 from respondents is considered as a sign of customers buying impulsiveness. Therefore, the mean of 3.03 along with a standard deviation of 0.631 (table-2) may allow us to conclude that our sample has a tendency of impulse buying to a certain extent. A list of items measuring customers' impulse buying tendency is presented in table-2.

Testing of hypotheses:

Analysis of customers' impulse buying tendency based on age:

The table-3 shows descriptive statistics for impulse buying tendency among customers with various age groups. The age is measured in four groups: 16-20 years, 21-25 years, 26-30 years and 31 – 35 years. As we can see in table-3, the data do not provide sufficient information to draw the conclusion that the more young people are, the more impulsive they might be. The table-4 shows the result of one way ANOVA to test the differences in customers' impulse buying tendency on the basis of age. The results (p > 0.05) indicate that age has no significant effect on the impulse buying tendency at 5% level of significance.

Hence H₁ is rejected.

Table-3: Descriptive statistics for age based analysis

Particulars	Age group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Impulse Buying Tendency	16-20 years	165	2.98	0.70
	21-25 years	366	3.10	0.79
	26-30 years	126	2.92	0.79
	31-35 years	20	2.95	0.59
	Total	677	3.04	0.77

Source: Primary source

Table-4: ANOVA of age based analysis

Particulars		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Impulse Buying Tendency	Between groups	3.859	3	1.286	2.180	0.089
	Within groups	397.152	673	0.590		
	Total	401.012	676			

Source: Primary source

Analysis of customers' impulse buying tendency based on gender:

As shown in table-5, comparing the means between the two genders obtained through the study, the female gender appears to have more impulse buying tendency (mean=3.13) than the male gender (mean=2.95). An independent sample t-test is used to understand whether impulse buying tendency differed based on gender. The table-6 shows the results of the impulse buying tendency of customers according to the gender variable. The results indicate that there is a significant difference between the impulse buying tendency of male and female customers [$t(df=675) = -2.963, p = 0.003$] at the 5% level of significance. **Hence H₂ is accepted.**

Table-5: Descriptive statistics for gender based analysis

Particulars	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Impulse Buying Tendency	Male	357	2.95	0.77
	Female	320	3.13	0.76

Source: Primary source

Table-6: Independent sample t test for gender based analysis

Particulars	t-test for Equality of Means		
	t	df	Sig.(2-tailed)
Impulse Buying Tendency	-2.963	675	0.003

Source: Primary source

Analysis of customers' impulse buying tendency based on occupation:

Table-7 shows that impulse buying tendency has a total mean score of 3.04 which indicates that customers have a tendency of impulse buying to a certain extent at various occupational levels. The table-8 shows the result of one way ANOVA to test the effect of occupation on impulse buying tendency. The variable occupation is measured in five groups: Employed, Unemployed, Professional, Business/others, and Student. The results (p

> 0.05) indicate that there is no significant difference in the impulse buying tendency of the customers with different occupational status. Hence H₃ is rejected.

Table-7: Descriptive Statistics for occupation based analysis

Particulars	Occupation	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Impulse Buying Tendency	Employed	285	3.02	0.81
	Unemployed	45	3.06	0.76
	Professional	29	3.14	0.91
	Business / others	13	3.00	0.77
	Student	305	3.04	0.72
	Total	677	3.04	0.77

Source: Primary source

Table-8: ANOVA of occupation based analysis

Particulars		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Impulse Buying Tendency	Between groups	0.444	4	0.111	0.186	0.946
	Within groups	400.568	672	0.596		
	Total	401.012	676			

Source: Primary source

Analysis of customers' impulse buying tendency based on marital status:

According to table-9, there is no much difference in the mean score of single (mean=3.05) and married (mean=2.97) customers for impulse buying tendency. The table-10 presents the results of t test, which tests the difference between the opinion of single and married customers towards impulse buying tendency. The results indicate that there is no significant difference between the opinion of single and married customers towards impulse buying tendency at 5 % level of significance. Hence H₄ is rejected.

Table-9: Descriptive statistics for marital status based analysis

Particulars	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Impulse Buying Tendency	Single	591	3.05	0.77
	Married	86	2.97	0.75

Source: Primary source

Table-10: Independent sample t test for marital status based analysis

Particulars	t-test for Equality of Means		
	t	df	Sig.(2-tailed)
Impulse Buying Tendency	0.832	675	0.406

Source: Primary source

Analysis of customers' impulse buying tendency based on qualification:

The variable occupation is measured in four groups:Intermediate, Graduation, Post-Graduation, and other. As we can see in table 11, there is a mere difference in the mean scores of respondents with different educational qualification. Thus the data don't provide

sufficient information to draw the conclusion that the customers' impulse buying tendency varies across various educational qualifications.

Table-11: Descriptive statistics for educational qualification based analysis

Particulars	Qualification	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Impulse Buying Tendency	Intermediate	226	3.01	0.75
	Graduation	231	3.07	0.85
	Post-Graduation	203	3.02	0.69
	Other	17	3.08	0.83
	Total	677	3.04	0.77

Source: Primary source

In addition to that, table-12 shows the result of one way ANOVA to test the effect of educational qualification on impulse buying tendency. The results indicate that occupation has no significant effect on the customers' impulse buying tendency at 5% level of significance. Hence H5 is rejected.

Table-12: ANOVA of educational qualification based analysis

Particulars		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Impulse Buying Tendency	Between groups	0.432	3	0.144	0.242	0.867
	Within groups	400.580	673	0.595		
	Total	401.012	676			

Source: Primary source

Analysis of customers' impulse buying tendency based on income:

The independent variable income is measured in five groups: Below Rs. 10000, Rs. 10000-25000, Rs. 26000-50000, and Rs.51000 and above and Dependent on parents' /others' income. Table-13 shows the customers who belong to the income group Rs.51000 and above have more impulse buying tendency than others with a mean score of 3.3. The table-14 shows the result of one way ANOVA to test the effect of income on customers' impulse buying tendency. The results indicate that income has no significant effect on customers' impulse buying tendency as p-value (0.076) is greater than 0.05. Hence H6 is rejected.

Table-13: Descriptive statistics for income based analysis

Particulars	Occupation	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Impulse Buying Tendency	Below Rs. 10000	52	2.95	0.82
	Rs. 10000-25000	178	3.05	0.77
	Rs. 26000-50000	6	2.88	0.80
	Rs.51000 and above	37	3.30	0.86
	Dependent on parents/others income	324	3.05	0.73
	Total	677	3.04	0.77

Source: Primary source

Table-14: ANOVA of income based analysis

Particulars		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Impulse Buying	Between groups	5.010	4	1.252	2.125	0.076
	Within groups	396.002	672	0.589		
Tendency	Total	401.012	676			

Source: Primary source

Conclusion:

From the above results we have reached the conclusion that the demographic factors of customers such age, marital status, income, educational qualification and occupation have no significant effect on young customers’ impulse buying behaviour. However, our study shows that gender has a significant impact on impulse buying behaviour. The results indicate that there is a significant difference between the impulse buying tendency of male and female customers. The female gender appears to have more impulse buying tendency than the male gender. The results revealed that only one demographic factor viz., gender is significantly affecting the customers’ impulsiveness. The remaining demographic factors have not shown any significant impact on impulse buying in the current research.

Limitations and future research:

The sample was limited by demographic variable of age (16-35 years) which limits generalizability of results to other customers. The research was conducted only on the customers of shopping malls in Bangalore city for apparel category which again limits generalisations. Results may differ for customers of other cities or other age-groups because of sociocultural and socio-demographic differences. These limitations lead to a recommendation that further research studies should use samples from different geographic locations and age-groups to provide further evidence to verify the findings of the study. A future research may be undertaken to make a comparison between the impulse buying behaviour in Tier II and III cities. The impulse buying behaviour of customers in malls can be compared with that of local retailers. The personality traits of the consumers have not been included in data collection. These variables can be taken up in future research for analysing their effect on impulse buying behaviour. Finally, since impulse buying is presumed to be largely universal, research should investigate cultural differences in impulse buying behaviour.

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